

Chemical Examination of *Acalypha indica*

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Acalypha indica (Euphorbiaceae) is a weed, widely distributed throughout the plains of India. The plant is reported to be useful in pneumonia, asthma etc. and to have some potency as a substitute for senega¹. A chemical examination of the whole plant is reported in this communication.

Dried and powdered whole plant (200 g.) was extracted with benzene in a Soxhlet apparatus for 8 hr. The gummy residue (7.3 g.) left after removal of benzene was dissolved in ether and extracted with cold 3% sodium hydroxide solution. The aqueous layer on acidification with cold dilute hydrochloric acid yielded a gummy residue (0.68 g.), which was directly esterified with diazomethane (prepared from 1 g. of nitrosomethyl urea). The crude methyl ester on chromatography over a column of deactivated alumina (100 g.) yielded no crystalline material.

The above ether layer was washed with water, dried (Na_2SO_4) and evaporated to furnish a dark green gum (4.44 g.), which was chromatographed over a column of deactivated alumina (100 g.). Elution with a mixture of petroleum ether and benzene (1:1) yielded a fraction (0.68 g.), which on rechromatography and crystallisation from petroleum ether yielded a solid (0.62 g.), m.p. 85-86°. This solid gave negative tetranitromethane test and was not investigated. Further elution with a mixture of benzene and ether (2:1) yielded a second fraction (0.74 g.), which on rechromatography over a column of alumina (150 g.) and elution with the same solvent mixture yielded a solid (0.19 g.), m.p. 134-136°. This solid was directly acetylated without purification with acetic anhydride (1.9 ml.) and pyridine (1.9 ml.). The acetate (0.14 g.), m.p. 136-137°, which crystallised out of the reaction mixture was filtered and recrystallised from acetone to yield γ -sitosterol acetate, m.p. 137-139°, $[\alpha]_D^{20} -41^\circ$ (chloroform). The mixed m.p. with an authentic specimen was not depressed. (Found: C, 81.43; H, 11.36. $\text{C}_{31}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}_2$ requires: C, 81.52; H, 11.48%).

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